

Evaluation of in Vivo Antioxidant Potential of Garlic Derived Phytochemical Allicin in Different liver Cancer Cell Lines

Nayak Shyama Prasad Gopal
Research Scholar

Deptt. of Zoology. L. N. Mithila University, Darbhanga, Bihar

and

Dr. Shushovan Banik
Assistant Professor

University Deptt. of Zoology. L.N.Mithila University, Ddarbhanga, Bihar

Abstract: Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.), a member of the Lillaceae family, is a bulbous perennial plant that originated in central Asia, northeastern Iran, or the Kiegiz Desert of Western Russia. Garlic is also known as ajo, nectar of the gods, camphor of the poor, poor man's treacle, rustic treacle, and stinking rose. Garlic is among one of the world's oldest cultivated plants and has developed a long-standing reputation across many cultures for embodying therapeutic properties. Cancer preventive potential of natural products, especially phytochemicals, has gained tremendous attention since epidemiological data indicated that consumption of plant-based foods, including fruits and vegetables, is associated with a reduced risk of cancer. Garlic consists of several bioactive compounds that contribute to its many health benefits and pharmacological activities. Several studies on experimentally induced cancers in animal models and their amelioration using crude garlic extract, garlic powder, or isolated garlic phytochemicals such as allicin and other compounds have shown that garlic and its chemical derivatives have immense potential to fight cancers. Garlic is recognized to have potent anticancer efficacy due to the presence of several organic and sulfur components. These compounds affect multiple stages of cancer cell proliferation, development, growth, migration, invasion, and metastasis by interfering with cell cycle regulation, inhibiting cell signaling pathways, apoptosis induction, autophagy, and antioxidant potential. Bioactive compounds found in garlic include organic sulfides, saponins, phenolic compounds, and polysaccharides. Other constituents include water, lipids, fiber, proteins, vitamins, and minerals.

Key-Words: Garlic, Allicin, Antioxidant, Potential and Cancer.

INTRODUCTION:

Cancer preventive potential of natural products, especially phytochemicals, has gained tremendous attention since epidemiological data indicated that consumption of plant-based foods, including fruits and vegetables, is associated with a reduced risk of cancer.¹ Results of various preclinical and clinical studies during the last few decades encourage the development of plant secondary metabolites and bioactive food components for prevention and treatment of cancer. Natural agents, including plant products, have been extensively used for development of new anticancer drugs, and more than 60 % of the currently approved anticancer drugs are derived from natural sources. Natural remedies have been used extensively to cure human illnesses since ancient times, and they are now being used as a key resource in drug development studies. The best hope for cancer patients is either early diagnosis or surgical tumor removal followed by radiation therapy and chemotherapy. Nevertheless, cancer continues to be one of the major cause of mortality across the globe and demands an urgent need for developing effective ways to combat morbidity and mortality along with high economic costs. In-depth research on phytochemicals has shown that they have anticarcinogenic

properties, which affect cancer initiation, proliferation, and progression *via* regulating numerous pathways, such as differentiation, cell proliferation, apoptosis, invasion, angiogenesis, metastasis, and migration. *Allium sativum* L., also recognized as garlic, is a member of the Alliaceae family. The term Alliaceae comes from the Celtic word “all,” which means strong and nature’s gift to mankind. The bulbs of garlic range in color from white to pink having a pungent scent and fragrant flavor.²The therapeutic and preventive properties of garlic against numerous cancers have been assessed by several epidemiologic, preclinical, and clinical investigations. *Allium sativum* extracts have been shown to have numerous biological properties including antiviral, antiprotozoal, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, and antioxidant activities. The anti-cancerous potential of garlic has been validated by many preclinical studies using human cancer cells, including those of the lung, mouth, stomach, pancreas, ovary, endometrium, breast, liver, prostate, and bone cancer.³ Further, laboratory experimentation has demonstrated that chemical components reported in garlic can repair DNA damage, induce cancer cell growth arrest, and reduce inflammatory responses.

Nanotechnology aims to improve the ability of drugs to effectively treat cancer by ensuring that they are delivered to the right target at the right times. Recently, nanotechnology-based delivery approaches have drawn wider attention as a potential solution to issues related with drug solubility and bioavailability, toxicity, and distribution. Novel approaches incorporating the therapeutic characteristics of garlic extracts and their constituents, either alone or in nanoparticle formulations, may thus result in more efficient and effective anticancer activity.⁴ Nanobiotechnology has gained attention in the last 20 years as a field of study that has influenced the development of new medications. Due to their low volume/surface ratio and several advanced and novel physicochemical properties, such as color, solubility, strength, toxicity, magnetic, optical, and thermodynamics, nanomaterial, the topic of our investigation, differ significantly from their macro scale counterparts in terms of capabilities. Mechanism associated with nanoparticles biogenesis include reduction of metallic ions of numerous biomolecules found in living things. The manufacture of vast amounts of well-defined, contaminant-free nanoparticles with defined size and morphology is made possible by nanoparticle biogenesis, which also lessens the environmental impact of biological synthesis. Recent nanotechnological advancements demonstrated the synthesis of nanoparticles utilizing the potential of microorganisms and plant based materials (tissue and extracts) including garlic constituents.

Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.), a member of the Lillaceae family, is a bulbous perennial plant that originated in central Asia, northeastern Iran, or the Kiegiz Desert of Western Russia. Garlic is among one of the world’s oldest cultivated plants and has developed a long-standing reputation across many cultures for embodying therapeutic properties.⁶ Historically, garlic has been used as a culinary seasoning, condiment, therapeutic agent, and for its medicinal value. Ancient medical texts from the Babylonians, Egyptians, Greeks, Romans, Chinese, Indians, and Israelis have all acknowledged garlic as a therapeutic agent for many physiological disorders and health-related ailments. Garlic consists of several bioactive compounds that contribute to its many health benefits and pharmacological activities. Bioactive compounds found in garlic include organic sulfides, saponins, phenolic compounds, and polysaccharides. Other constituents include water, lipids, fiber, proteins, vitamins, and minerals. Several recent studies have reported numerous health benefits of garlic, including anti-inflammatory, antiangiogenic, antidiabetic, antiarthritic, antihyperglycemic, anticoagulant, antispasmodic, antihistaminic, antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal and antiparasitic effects.⁷ Other therapeutic effects of garlic include reducing oxidative stress, lowering hyperlipidemia and hypertension, promoting prostanoids synthesis, accelerating immune enhancement, and suppressing osteoarthritis and osteoporosis as well as protecting cardiac and hepatic functions. In regard to cancer, epidemiological studies have demonstrated garlic's negative association with a variety of cancer types, with most of these effects mentioned being attributed mainly to the organosulfur compounds (OSCs) of garlic. Phytochemical analysis of garlic revealed the presence of both bioactive sulfur-containing and non-sulfur-containing chemical compounds. Garlic is a rich source of OSCs with more than 33 different types of OSCs. These compounds contribute to its characteristic flavor, taste and health benefits. The garlic bulb contains ~65 % water, ~28 % carbohydrates, ~2.3 % OSCs, ~2% protein, ~1.2 % free amino acids, and ~1.5 % fiber as well as fatty acids, phenols, and trace

elements.⁸ Although further studies regarding the activity of allicin on normal cells and the details of the mechanism of action of allicin on neoplasms and the most efficient routes of administration are required. Further studies would also decipher its molecular interactions within the living system so that its claimed applicability long-term and cost-effective benefits in assume terms of health and nutrition among consumers to create a cancer-free world.

METHODOLOGY:

The standard methodologies for analyses of enzymic antioxidants in untreated controls and allicin treated Cultured cell lines were taken up and are presented under the following subheadings :

Peroxidase Assay: Cell Biolabs[®] Oxi Select™ hydrogen peroxide/peroxidase assay kit was used to assay the activity of Peroxidase.

Catalase Activity Assay: Cell Bio labs[®] Oxi Select™ catalase activity Assay was used for the direct measurement of catalase activity from cell lysate.

Superoxide Dismutase Activity Assay: Oxi Select™ superoxide dismutase activity assay kit was used to assay superoxide dismutase activity in which a xanthine/xanthine oxidase (XOD) system generates superoxide anions.

GST Activity Assay: Sigma GST Activity Assay Kit (Colorimetric) was used to measure the activity of Glutathione-S-transferase (GST).

RESULTS:

The results of the analyses of Peroxidase activity in untreated and allicin treated cell lines show statistically significant increase in the activities of the said enzyme on treatment with increasing concentrations of allicin (i.e 0.01 μM , 0,1 μM and 1.0 μM).

The results of the analyses of Catalase activity in untreated and Allicin treated cell lines show statistically significant increase in the activity of the said enzyme on treatment with increasing concentrations of allicin (i.e 0.01 μM , 0,1 μM and 1.0 μM).

The results of the analyses of Superoxide Dismutase activity in untreated and Allicin treated cell lines show statistically significant increase in the enzyme activity on treatment with increasing concentrations of Allicin (i.e 0.01 μM , 0,1 μM , and 1.0 μM).

The results of the analyses of Glutathione S Transferase activity in untreated and Allicin treated cell lines show a statistically significant increase in the activity of the said enzyme on treatment with increasing concentrations of Allicin (i.e 0.01 μM , 0.1 μM and 1.0 μM).

DISCUSSIONS:

Garlic is recognized to have potent anticancer efficacy due to the presence of several organic and sulfur components. These compounds affect multiple stages of cancer cell proliferation, development, growth, migration, invasion, and metastasis by interfering with cell cycle regulation, inhibiting cell signaling pathways, apoptosis induction, autophagy, and antioxidant potential. The sulfur compounds in garlic are both fat- and water-soluble and demonstrate anticancer effects by reducing oxidative stress, metabolizing carcinogens, and boosting immune response. The therapeutic potential of garlic nanoformulations was higher than that of the photo component alone. For instance, allicin nanoparticles showed a stronger anti-angiogenesis impact than allicin by itself. In addition to providing targeted drug delivery, the use of NDDSs for drug delivery can increase the bioavailability of medications that are poorly water-soluble, allow for the co-delivery of several medications, prevent drug toxicity in normal cells, and extend the duration of therapeutic activity. In order to show their potential anticancer actions, nanoformulations have been used to deliver parent chemicals directly to the crucial locations of the malignant tissues. Nanoscale materials are used as carriers for delivering medications to their sites of action in NDDSs, which is a rapidly evolving field of science.

In the past decades, there has been an increased interest in using herbal medicines in the management, prevention, and therapy for a wide range of human diseases, including cancer. The herbal formulations from Ayurveda, traditional Chinese medicines, Japanese (Kampo), and others are composed of a mixture of different herbs, which synergistically work to produce maximum treatment efficacy with minimum or no side effects. Extensive research in the very arena has revealed that these formulations can down-regulate cancer cells progression and stimulate the immune system to rise against cancer. Garlic

and its components & products have also been found to have anticancer activities through diverse mechanisms. Several studies on experimentally induced cancers in animal models and their amelioration using crude garlic extract, garlic powder, or isolated garlic phytochemicals such as allicin and other compounds have shown that garlic and its chemical derivatives have immense potential to fight cancers. Allium species are supposed to be one of the world's oldest cultivated vegetables of the world. It is presumed that our ancestors consumed wild Allium species long before actual farming methods were invented. Allium plants are small in size and leave no archaeological evidence; their exact origin still remains a mystery. Allium species are characterized by their rich content of thiosulfinates and other organosulfur compounds.⁹ The thiosulfinates are formed by the action of the enzyme alliinase from their respective S-alk(en)yl cysteine sulfoxides, which are mainly responsible for flavor and smell of garlic and onion. The eye irritating compounds that induce tears are also a result of these sulphur rich compounds hence called Lachrymatory factors. Moreover, depending upon Allium species and differing conditions, thiosulfinates can decompose to form additional sulfur constituents, including diallyl, methyl allyl and diethyl mono-, di-, tri-, tetra-, penta- and hexasulfides, vinyl dithiols, etc. This piece of work examines the biological activities of Allium thiosulfinate, allicin, as anticancer nutraceuticals. As already described, Allicin (diallyl thiosulfinate or diallyl sulphide) is a biologically active compound found in crushed garlic due to stress-induced activation of an enzyme called alliinase that converts its precursor, alliin (S-allyl cysteine sulphoxide) into allicin. Studies throughout the globe on the efficiency of allicin during the last two decades have shown its overwhelming potential to cure many chronic degenerative diseases that had threatened mankind for a long time.¹⁰

The work emphasizes the utility of this multifaceted Nutraceutical allicin on cancer. Furthermore, allicin has shown a tremendous potential to modulate the immune system that constantly invigilates the body tissues for tumorigenic activities and help to clear off transformed cells were ever encountered.¹¹ In connection to these, research has also revealed the immense antioxidant potential of allicin which impart prevention and protection against free radical-induced damages. The terms "free radicals" and "active oxygen" have attracted the attention of large numbers of scientific workers and clinicians. Human beings face constant attacks by exogenous factors such as ultraviolet rays and tobacco smoke, which cause oxidative stress. Such stress also arises from drugs (including anticancer drugs) that are used in common medical practice. In addition to those exogenous sources, endogenous sources of oxidative stress include those which are derived from metabolic activities of mitochondria or microsomes, peroxisomes during the electron transfer, and those from the enzymes used by macrophages and neutrophils during the immune response. Reactive oxygen species may be involved in carcinogenesis through two possible mechanisms that induce mutations and the effects of signal transduction and transcription factors. The mechanism of damage induction depends on factors such as the type of active oxygen species involved and the intensity of stress. Active oxygen species are supposed to act directly or indirectly via effects on gene expression and cell signaling, and communications. As examples, Glutathione and Thioredoxin work in the mechanisms of redox regulation.¹² In general, cancer therapy with drugs and radiation creates a state of oxidative stress in the body, and active oxygen triggers apoptosis of exposed cells and cytochrome release from mitochondria. Anticancer drugs such as anthracyclines, bleomycin, mitomycin C and cisplatin have active oxygen mechanisms of activity.

The results of our study well correlate with the fact that as strong antioxidant properties impart radioprotective effects by free radical scavenging abilities and increase the efficiency of scavenging systems in the cells. Allicin has been shown to have pronounced antitumor activity in hepatocellular cancer cells through ROS-mediated mitochondrial pathways. It was reported by scientists that the antioxidant defense system changed in various human tumors. It was reported that a reverse relationship was found between antioxidant enzyme activities and lipid peroxidation in patients with tumor of various types. Alteration in the tissue and serum level activities of superoxide dismutase and other free radical scavengers have been studied in various pathological conditions about tumours and cancers. In connection to the above studies Iwase et al., 1997, however, reported that obtained data remains unclear as the activity of superoxide dismutase very greatly according to the alterations of conditions in each of the different study groups. Studies have shown that there is a general increase in total activity of

superoxide dismutase in the plasma and tissue samples of various subjects of malignant liver cancer. Furthermore significant increase in tissue activity of superoxide dismutase was recorded in malignant tumours as compared to benign tumors.¹³ In general, an increase in the superoxide dismutase activity might reflect our response to oxidative stress and thus may predict a state of increased stress of relative oxygen species in the process of carcinogenesis. In our study, the total activity of superoxide dismutase in liver cancer tissues was found to be higher than that of the control group, although the differences were statistically insignificant on treatment with allicin.¹⁴

CONCLUSION:

The present study aimed at analyzing the effectiveness of garlic-derived phytochemical, „allicin“ on cultured human liver cancer cell lines to analyze the alterations in the activity of enzymic antioxidants such as Peroxidase, Catalase, Superoxide dismutase, and GST in such cells. It was found that allicin treatment significantly increased the activities of the enzymes mentioned above in cultured cancer cells as compared to untreated control. The findings of this study throw a glimpse of light towards the development of plant-derived or herbal drugs to fight the dreaded disease as such drugs are cost-effective and free from side effects. Garlic is a phytochemically rich and versatile vegetable that has been used for centuries for its unique nutritive, flavor, and medicinal capabilities. Throughout the centuries, garlic has been shown to be utilized therapeutically for the treatment of asthma, diarrhea, constipation, infectious disease, hypertension, and fever as well as for its antiseptic ability . The earliest use of garlic for its anticancer properties dates back thousands of years to Egypt.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: The researcher would like to thank deptt. of zoology Laboratories, L.N.MITHILA, University ,Darbhanga for providing technical support and assistance for the successful completion of the said work.

REFERENCES:

1. Malla R., Marni R., Chakraborty A., Kamal M. A. (2021). Diallyl disulfide and diallyl trisulfide in garlic as novel therapeutic agents to overcome drug resistance in breast cancer. *J. Pharm. Analysis* 12, Pp.221–231.
2. Viswanathan V., Phadatare A. G., Mukne A. (2014). Antimycobacterial and antibacterial activity of *Allium sativum* bulbs. *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.* 76 (3), Pp.256–261.
3. Abdullah TH, Kandil O, Elkadi A and Carter J: Garlic revisited: therapeutic for the major diseases of our times. *J Natl Med Assoc* 1988; 80:Pp. 439-45.
4. Ibid
5. Chandra-Kuntal K., Lee J., Singh S. V. (2013). Critical role for reactive oxygen species in apoptosis induction and cell migration inhibition by diallyl trisulfide, a cancer chemopreventive component of garlic. *Breast cancer Res. Treat.* 138 (1), Pp.69–79.
6. Mandal S. K., Das A., Dey S., Sahoo U., Bose S., Bose A., et al. (2019). Bioactivities of Allicin and related organosulfur compounds from garlic: Overview of the literature since 2010. *Egypt. J. Chem.* 62, 0–11. Special Issue (Part 1).
7. Ibid
8. Ibid
9. Viswanathan V., Phadatare A. G., Mukne A. (2014). Antimycobacterial and antibacterial activity of *Allium sativum* bulbs. *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.* 76 (3), Pp.256–261.
10. Patya M: Allicin stimulates lymphocytes and elicits an anti-tumor effect: A possible role of p21ras. *Int Immunol* 2004; 16: Pp.275-81.
11. Dhanarasu S. (2017). Protective role of allicin (diallyl thiosulfinate) on cell surface glycoconjugate moieties in 7, 12-dimethylbenz (a) anthracene-induced oral carcinogenesis. *Trop. J. Pharm. Res.* 16 (8), Pp.1797–1804.
12. Pütter J and Becker R: In methods of enzymatic analysis bergmeyer. *IJPSR* 1983; 3: Pp,286-93.
13. Vijayakumar S., Malaikozhundan B., Saravanakumar K., Durán-Lara E. F., Wang M. H., Vaseeharan B. (2019). Garlic clove extract assisted silver nanoparticle–Antibacterial, antibiofilm, antihelminthic, anti-inflammatory, anticancer and ecotoxicity assessment. *J. Photochem. Photobiol. B: Biol.* 198,

14. Baecker A., Liu X., Vecchia C.L., Zhang Z.-F. Worldwide Incident Liver Cancer Cases Attributable to Six Major Risk Factors by Geographical Region. *Eur. J. Cancer Prev.* in press.
15. Zhao J.-K., Wu M., Kim C.H., Jin Z.-Y., Zhou J.-Y., Han R.-Q., Yang J., Zhang X.-F., Wang X.-S., Liu A.-M., et al. Jiangsu Four Cancers Study: A large case-control study of lung, liver, stomach and esophageal cancers in Jiangsu Province, China. *Eur. J. Cancer Prev. Off. J. Eur. Cancer Prev. Organ. ECP.* 2017.
16. Singh V., Belloir C., Siess M.-H., Le Bon A.-M. Inhibition of carcinogen-induced DNA damage in rat liver and colon by garlic powders with varying alliin content. *Nutr. Cancer.* 2006;55:178–184
17. Kakkar PS, Das B and Viswanathan PN: A modified spectrophotometric assay of superoxide dismutase. *Ind J Biochem Biophys* 1984; 21: Pp.130-32.
18. Habig WH, Pabst MJ and Jacoby WB: Glutathione S-transferases: the first enzymatic step in mercapturic acid formation. *J Biol Chem* 1974;p. 249:
19. Rao DN, Desai PB and Ganesh B: Epidemiological observation on cancer of the esophagus- a review of Indian studies. *Ind J Cancer* 1976; 33: Pp.55-75
20. Ghosh S., Javia A., Shetty S., Bardoliwala D., Maiti K., Banerjee S., et al. (2021). Triple negative breast cancer and non-small cell lung cancer: Clinical challenges and nano-formulation approaches. *J. Control. Release* 337, Pp. 27–58.
21. Menon D., Basanth A., Retnakumari A., Manzoor K., Nair S. V. (2012). Green synthesis of biocompatible gold nanocrystals with tunable surface plasmon resonance using garlic phytochemicals. *J. Biomed. Nanotechnol.* 8 (6), Pp. 901–911.
22. Mondal A., Banerjee S., Bose S., Mazumder S., Haber R. A., Farzaei M. H., et al. (2022). Garlic constituents for cancer prevention and therapy: From phytochemistry to novel formulations. *Pharmacol. Res.* 175,
23. Ranjan A., Ramachandran S., Gupta N., Kaushik I., Wright S., Srivastava S., et al. (2019). Role of phytochemicals in cancer prevention. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 20 (20), P. 4981.
24. Shashikant K. N., Basappa S. C., Sreenivasamurthy V. (1985). Allicin concentration in the gut of rats and its influence on the microflora. *J. food Sci. Technol.* 22 (6), Pp. 440–442.
25. Shukla Y., Kalra N. (2007). Cancer chemoprevention with garlic and its constituents. *Cancer Lett.* 247 (2), Pp.167–181.
26. Vijayakumar S., Malaikozhundan B., Saravanakumar K., Durán-Lara E. F., Wang M. H., Vaseeharan B. (2019). Garlic clove extract assisted silver nanoparticle–Antibacterial, antibiofilm, antihelminthic, anti-inflammatory, anticancer and ecotoxicity assessment. *J. Photochem. Photobiol. B: Biol.* 198,
27. Baecker A., Liu X., Vecchia C.L., Zhang Z.-F. Worldwide Incident Liver Cancer Cases Attributable to Six Major Risk Factors by Geographical Region. *Eur. J. Cancer Prev.* in press.
28. Zhao J.-K., Wu M., Kim C.H., Jin Z.-Y., Zhou J.-Y., Han R.-Q., Yang J., Zhang X.-F., Wang X.-S., Liu A.-M., et al. Jiangsu Four Cancers Study: A large case-control study of lung, liver, stomach and esophageal cancers in Jiangsu Province, China. *Eur. J. Cancer Prev. Off. J. Eur. Cancer Prev. Organ. ECP.* 2017.
29. .